

Log-concavity of domination polynomials for spiders with legs of length at most three

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Abstract

Let $S_{a,b,c}$ be the spider with a legs of length 1, b legs of length 2, and c legs of length 3. We prove that, for all $a, b, c \geq 0$, not all zero, the nonzero coefficient sequence of the domination polynomial $D(S_{a,b,c}, x)$ is log-concave. In particular, every such spider has a unimodal domination polynomial. The proof starts from an explicit short-legged spider formula and reduces the problem to two families of coefficient inequalities for

$$A(x)^c = (1 + 3x + 2x^2)^c, \quad B(x)^c = (1 + 3x + x^2)^c.$$

The required inequalities are proved by ratio estimates, a binomial-basis weak-synchronization argument, and an exact finite verification of cleared integer inequalities. A reproducible exact-arithmetic verifier is included as an ancillary file.

1 Introduction

For a finite graph G , the domination polynomial is

$$D(G, x) = \sum_{k \geq 0} d(G, k)x^k,$$

where $d(G, k)$ is the number of dominating sets of G of cardinality k . Alikhani and Peng introduced the domination polynomial in this form and posed the unimodality problem for its coefficients [1]. Beaton and Brown proved the conjecture for paths, cycles, complete multipartite graphs, and almost all graphs [2]. Burcroff and O'Brien later proved unimodality for several further families, including all spiders with at most 400 legs, where the bound comes from a finite computer check [3]. This note proves a structural log-concavity result for the subfamily in which every leg has length at most three.

A sequence (s_i) is *log-concave* if $s_i^2 \geq s_{i-1}s_{i+1}$ for every relevant i . Throughout, the assertion that the coefficient sequence of a polynomial is log-concave means that its nonzero coefficient sequence is log-concave. Since a nonnegative log-concave sequence with no internal zeros is unimodal, the following theorem implies unimodality.

Theorem 1. *Let $S_{a,b,c}$ be the spider with a legs of length 1, b legs of length 2, and c legs of length 3. For all $a, b, c \geq 0$, not all zero, the nonzero coefficient sequence of $D(S_{a,b,c}, x)$ is log-concave.*

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2 Preliminaries on log-concavity

We use the following standard closure properties.

Lemma 1 (closure properties). *Let (u_i) and (v_i) be nonnegative log-concave sequences without internal zeros.*

(i) *Their convolution is log-concave.*

(ii) *Their pointwise product $(u_i v_i)$ is log-concave.*

(iii) *Reversal and shifts by zeros preserve log-concavity of the nonzero part.*

Proof. Part (i) is Hoggar's convolution theorem [4]; see also the probabilistic formulation in [5]. Part (ii) follows by multiplying the two log-concavity inequalities. Part (iii) is immediate. \square

We shall also use the standard monotone-likelihood-ratio closure under convolution: if two pairs of nonnegative sequences (α, β) and (γ, δ) have no internal zeros and the ratios β_i/α_i and δ_i/γ_i are nonincreasing, then

$$(\beta * \delta)_i / (\alpha * \gamma)_i$$

is nonincreasing. This is the TP_2 convolution rule, equivalently an application of the Cauchy–Binet formula to Toeplitz matrices of log-concave sequences.

For a polynomial

$$E(x) = \prod_{j=1}^n (1 + w_j x) = \sum_{k=0}^n e_k x^k, \quad w_j > 0,$$

we repeatedly use Newton–Maclaurin inequalities in the form

$$\frac{e_{k+1}/e_k}{e_k/e_{k-1}} \leq \frac{k(n-k)}{(k+1)(n-k+1)}. \quad (1)$$

We also use the elementary extension bound

$$\frac{e_k}{e_{k-1}} \geq \frac{W - (k-1)w_{\max}}{k}, \quad (2)$$

where $W = \sum_j w_j$ and $w_{\max} = \max_j w_j$. Indeed, after a fixed $(k-1)$ -subset is chosen, the total weight available for extensions is at least $W - (k-1)w_{\max}$, and every k -subset is counted k times. When all $w_j \geq 1$, the sharper bound

$$\frac{e_k}{e_{k-1}} \geq \frac{n-k+1}{k} \quad (3)$$

follows in the same way.

3 The short-legged spider formula

Let z be the center of $S_{a,b,c}$. Counting dominating sets according as they contain z gives the following explicit formula. If $a > 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} D(S_{a,b,c}, x) &= x(1+x)^a (2x+x^2)^b (2x+3x^2+x^3)^c \\ &\quad + x^a (2x+x^2)^b (x+3x^2+x^3)^c. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

If $a = 0$, then

$$D(S_{0,b,c}, x) = x(2x+x^2)^b (2x+3x^2+x^3)^c$$

$$+ (2x + x^2)^b(x + 3x^2 + x^3)^c - x^b(x + x^2)^c. \quad (5)$$

The subtraction in (5) removes exactly the cases in which z is not selected and no neighbor of z is selected.

Set

$$A(x) = 1 + 3x + 2x^2 = (1 + x)(1 + 2x), \quad B(x) = 1 + 3x + x^2,$$

and

$$C(x) = 2 + 3x + x^2 = (1 + x)(x + 2).$$

For $a > 0$, after removing the harmless factor $x^{b+c+1}(x + 2)^b$ and reversing coefficients, (4) reduces to

$$P_{a,c}(x) = (1 + x)^a A(x)^c + xB(x)^c. \quad (6)$$

For $a = 0$, after removing the harmless factor x^{b+c} , (5) reduces to

$$R_{b,c}(x) = (x + 2)^b \{B(x)^c + xC(x)^c\} - (1 + x)^c. \quad (7)$$

By Lemma 1, Theorem 1 follows once we prove log-concavity of (6) for all $a, c \geq 0$ and of (7) for all $b, c \geq 0$.

4 Two coefficient-ratio estimates

Fix $c \geq 0$ and write

$$a_k = [x^k]A(x)^c, \quad b_k = [x^k]B(x)^c,$$

with $a_k = b_k = 0$ outside $0 \leq k \leq 2c$. For $1 \leq k \leq 2c$ put

$$q_k = \frac{b_k}{a_k}, \quad r_k = \frac{a_k}{a_{k-1}},$$

and set $q_0 = 1$.

Lemma 2 (monotone likelihood ratio). *The sequence $(q_k)_{0 \leq k \leq 2c}$ is nonincreasing.*

Proof. For one quadratic factor, the coefficientwise ratios of B to A are

$$1, \quad 1, \quad \frac{1}{2},$$

which are nonincreasing. The TP_2 convolution closure for monotone likelihood-ratio order gives the same assertion after taking c -fold powers. \square

Lemma 3 (ratio drop for A^c). *For $c \geq 1$ and $1 \leq k \leq 2c$, with $r_{2c+1} = 0$,*

$$r_k - r_{k+1} \geq \frac{2c + 1}{k(k + 1)}. \quad (8)$$

Proof. The polynomial $A(x)^c = (1 + x)^c(1 + 2x)^c$ is an elementary-symmetric generating polynomial in $2c$ variables, all at least 1. Hence (3) gives

$$r_k \geq \frac{2c - k + 1}{k}.$$

Combining this with (1), with $n = 2c$, gives

$$r_k - r_{k+1} \geq r_k \left(1 - \frac{k(2c - k)}{(k + 1)(2c - k + 1)} \right) \geq \frac{2c + 1}{k(k + 1)}.$$

\square

Lemma 4 (curvature estimate). *For all $c \geq 1$ and $1 \leq k \leq 2c$,*

$$q_{k-1} - q_k \leq \frac{2c+1}{k(k+1)}. \quad (9)$$

Proof. The coefficients of $A(x)^c$ and $B(x)^c$ satisfy

$$ka_k = 3(c-k+1)a_{k-1} + 2(2c-k+2)a_{k-2}, \quad (10)$$

$$kb_k = 3(c-k+1)b_{k-1} + (2c-k+2)b_{k-2}. \quad (11)$$

Thus, for $2 \leq k \leq c+1$,

$$q_k = (1 - \mu_k)q_{k-1} + \frac{\mu_k}{2}q_{k-2}, \quad \mu_k = \frac{2(2c-k+2)a_{k-2}}{ka_k}.$$

Using (2) for $A(x)^c = (1+x)^c(1+2x)^c$ gives

$$\frac{a_{k-1}}{a_{k-2}} \geq \frac{3c-2k+4}{k-1} \quad (2 \leq k \leq c+1),$$

and substitution in (10) gives

$$\frac{\mu_k}{2} \leq \frac{k}{2c+1} \quad (2 \leq k \leq c+1). \quad (12)$$

Since q_k is nonincreasing,

$$q_{k-1} - q_k \leq \frac{k}{2c+1}q_{k-1} \quad (2 \leq k \leq c+1). \quad (13)$$

For $0 \leq s \leq c$ we also have

$$q_s \leq 2^{-s(s-1)/(9c)}. \quad (14)$$

Indeed, write

$$[x^s](1+3x+\lambda x^2)^c = \sum_{\nu} W_{s,\nu} \lambda^{\nu}.$$

With respect to the probability weights proportional to $W_{s,\nu}$ at $\lambda = 1$, Jensen's inequality gives $q_s^{-1} \geq 2^{\mathbb{E}\nu}$. Moreover,

$$\mathbb{E}\nu = \frac{c[x^{s-2}]B(x)^{c-1}}{[x^s]B(x)^c} \geq \frac{s(s-1)}{9c},$$

which follows from Maclaurin's inequalities applied to $B(x)^{c-1}$. This proves (14).

Let $C_0 = 2c+1$. For $c \geq 1471$, the following elementary inequalities hold:

$$2^{-(k-1)(k-2)/(9c)} \leq \frac{C_0^2}{k^2(k+1)} \quad \text{if } 2 \leq k \leq c+1 \text{ and } k^2(k+1) > C_0^2, \quad (15)$$

$$2^{-y-(c-y+1)(c-y)/(9c)} \leq \frac{2c+1}{(c+y)(c+y+1)} \quad \text{if } 2 \leq y \leq c. \quad (16)$$

They are checked by taking logarithms: in (15) put $z = (k+1)/C_0^{2/3} > 1$ and use $\log z \leq z^2/(2e)$ together with $C_0^{1/3} > 27/(e \log 2)$; in (16) the logarithm of the ratio of the right-hand side to the left-hand side is increasing for $y \geq 2$ and is already nonnegative at $y = 2$.

Now assume $2 \leq k \leq c+1$. If $k^2(k+1) \leq C_0^2$, then (13) gives (9). Otherwise combine (13), (14), and (15). For $c+2 \leq k \leq 2c$, write $k = c+y$ with $2 \leq y \leq c$. The reciprocal identities

$$a_{2c-s} = 2^{c-s}a_s, \quad b_{2c-s} = b_s$$

give

$$q_{k-1} - q_k = 2^{-y}\{2q_{c-y+1} - q_{c-y}\} \leq 2^{-y}q_{c-y+1}.$$

Then (14) and (16) prove the tail range. For $1 \leq c \leq 1470$, the cleared integer form of (9) is verified by the exact-arithmetic ancillary program. \square

Lemma 5 (shifted curvature estimate). *For all $c \geq 1$ and $1 \leq k \leq 2c - 2$,*

$$q_{k-1} - q_k \leq r_{k+1} - r_{k+2}, \quad (17)$$

where $r_{2c+1} = 0$.

Proof. For $1 \leq c \leq 1470$, the cleared integer form of (17) is verified by the ancillary program. Assume $c \geq 1471$.

For $2 \leq k \leq c + 1$, the same upper bound as in Lemma 4 is available from (13) and (14). By Lemma 3,

$$r_{k+1} - r_{k+2} \geq \frac{2c+1}{(k+1)(k+2)}.$$

If $k(k+1)(k+2) \leq (2c+1)^2$, then (13) is already at most this lower bound. If $k(k+1)(k+2) > (2c+1)^2$, the logarithmic argument used for (15), with $k(k+1)(k+2)$ in place of $k^2(k+1)$, gives

$$2^{-(k-1)(k-2)/(9c)} \leq \frac{(2c+1)^2}{k(k+1)(k+2)},$$

and (17) follows.

For $c+2 \leq k \leq 2c-2$, write $k = c+y$ with $2 \leq y \leq c-2$. As above,

$$q_{k-1} - q_k \leq 2^{-y-(c-y+1)(c-y)/(9c)}.$$

The slightly stronger tail inequality

$$2^{-y-(c-y+1)(c-y)/(9c)} \leq \frac{2c+1}{(c+y+1)(c+y+2)}$$

holds for $c \geq 1471$ by the same monotonicity-in- y proof as (16). Combining this with Lemma 3 proves the tail range. \square

5 The base polynomial

Theorem 2. *For every $c \geq 0$, the coefficient sequence of*

$$P_{0,c}(x) = A(x)^c + xB(x)^c$$

is log-concave.

Proof. Let $p_j = a_j + b_{j-1}$, with $b_{-1} = 0$. The cases $c = 0, 1$ are direct. For $1 \leq j \leq 2c$, write

$$p_j^2 - p_{j-1}p_{j+1} = \Delta_j^A + \Delta_{j-1}^B + C_j,$$

where

$$\Delta_j^A = a_j^2 - a_{j-1}a_{j+1} \geq 0, \quad \Delta_{j-1}^B = b_{j-1}^2 - b_{j-2}b_j \geq 0,$$

and

$$C_j = 2a_jb_{j-1} - a_{j-1}b_j - a_{j+1}b_{j-2}.$$

The endpoint cases $j = 1$ and $j = 2c$ are immediate. For $2 \leq j \leq 2c-1$, divide $\Delta_j^A + C_j$ by a_ja_{j-1} and put

$$u = q_{j-2} - q_{j-1}, \quad \lambda = \frac{r_{j+1}}{r_{j-1}} \in [0, 1].$$

Since $q_j \leq q_{j-1}$, one obtains

$$\frac{\Delta_j^A + C_j}{a_ja_{j-1}} \geq r_j - r_{j+1} - \lambda u.$$

By Lemma 5, applied with $k = j-1$, we have $u \leq r_j - r_{j+1}$. Hence $\Delta_j^A + C_j \geq 0$, and adding $\Delta_{j-1}^B \geq 0$ proves the theorem. \square

6 The weak-synchronization step for $a > 0$

For $m, c \geq 0$, set

$$U_{m,c}(x) = (1+x)^m A(x)^c, \quad P_{m,c}(x) = U_{m,c}(x) + xB(x)^c.$$

Write $u_i = [x^i]U_{m,c}(x)$ and $p_i = [x^i]P_{m,c}(x)$.

We need two adjacent consequences of Lemmas 4 and 3. Put

$$h_j = a_j - b_{j-1} \quad (b_{-1} = 0).$$

Lemma 6. *If $c \geq 4$, then $h_j \geq 0$ for $0 \leq j \leq 2c$ and the sequence h_j/a_{j-1} is nonincreasing for $1 \leq j \leq 2c$.*

Proof. For $1 \leq j \leq 2c$,

$$\frac{h_j}{a_{j-1}} = r_j - q_{j-1}.$$

Thus h_j/a_{j-1} is nonincreasing if $q_{j-2} - q_{j-1} \leq r_{j-1} - r_j$, which follows from Lemmas 4 and 3. At the right endpoint,

$$h_{2c} = a_{2c} - b_{2c-1} = 2^c - 3c \geq 0 \quad (c \geq 4).$$

Since h_j/a_{j-1} is nonincreasing in j , all earlier h_j are also nonnegative; $h_0 = 1$ separately. \square

Lemma 7. *For all $c \geq 0$ and $2 \leq j \leq 2c$,*

$$b_j a_{j-2} \leq b_{j-1} a_{j-1}. \quad (18)$$

Proof. By Lemma 2, $q_j = b_j/a_j$ is nonincreasing, and by log-concavity of $A(x)^c$, $r_j = a_j/a_{j-1}$ is nonincreasing. Hence $b_j/a_{j-1} = q_j r_j$ is nonincreasing in j , which is exactly (18). \square

Lemma 8 (mixed-gap inequality). *For all $m, c \geq 0$ and all i ,*

$$2p_i u_{i-1} - p_{i-1} u_i - p_{i+1} u_{i-2} \geq 0. \quad (19)$$

Proof. Expand the left side in the binomial basis in the parameter m :

$$2p_i u_{i-1} - p_{i-1} u_i - p_{i+1} u_{i-2} = \sum_{t \geq 0} E_{c,i,t} \binom{m}{t}.$$

Using

$$u_i = \sum_{r \geq 0} \binom{m}{r} a_{i-r}$$

and the identity

$$\binom{m}{r} \binom{m}{s} = \sum_{t=\max(r,s)}^{r+s} \frac{t!}{(r+s-t)!(t-r)!(t-s)!} \binom{m}{t},$$

one obtains $E_{c,i,t} = F_{c,i,t} + L_{c,i,t}$, where, with $n = i - t$,

$$F_{c,i,t} = \sum_{r+s+h=t} \frac{t!}{r!s!h!} (a_{n+s} a_{n+r-1} - a_{n+s+1} a_{n+r-2}),$$

$$L_{c,i,t} = 2b_{i-1} a_{n-1} - b_{i-2} a_n - b_i a_{n-2}.$$

All out-of-range coefficients are interpreted as zero.

For the product part, pair each negative minor

$$D(r, s) = a_{n+s}a_{n+r-1} - a_{n+s+1}a_{n+r-2}$$

with $D(s+2, r-2) = -D(r, s)$ whenever $r \geq s+3$. The paired multinomial coefficient is larger by the factor

$$\frac{r(r-1)}{(s+1)(s+2)} \geq 1.$$

Thus all negative summands in $F_{c,i,t}$ are cancelled. The unpaired summand $(r, s, h) = (0, t, 0)$ contributes

$$D_0 = a_i a_{n-1} - a_{i+1} a_{n-2},$$

and the t unpaired summands corresponding to $(r, s, h) = (1, t-1, 0)$ contribute

$$tD_1 = t(a_{i-1}a_n - a_i a_{n-1}).$$

Consequently

$$F_{c,i,t} \geq D_0 + tD_1. \quad (20)$$

There are three harmless boundary ranges. If $n < 0$, then the perturbation term $L_{c,i,t}$ vanishes and the same pairing already gives $E_{c,i,t} \geq 0$. If $i \geq 2c+3$, then again $L_{c,i,t} = 0$, and the product pairing gives $E_{c,i,t} \geq 0$. If $i = 2c+2$, then $L_{c,i,t} = -a_n$. When $a_n = 0$ there is nothing to prove; otherwise $0 \leq n \leq 2c$ and the unpaired positive summand $(r, s, h) = (1, 2c-n, 1)$ in $F_{c,i,t}$ contributes

$$(2c+2-n)(2c+1-n)2^c a_n \geq a_n,$$

so $E_{c,i,t} \geq 0$ in this boundary case as well.

It remains to prove the boundary-compensation inequality

$$\Phi_{c,i,t} := D_0 + tD_1 + L_{c,i,t} \geq 0 \quad (21)$$

in the range $0 \leq n \leq i \leq 2c+1$. For $c \leq 3$, this finite family is checked exactly by the ancillary verifier. Assume $c \geq 4$.

If $i = 2c+1$, then $t \geq 1$ unless $n = i$, in which case all terms vanish except the positive top terms. For $t \geq 1$ one has

$$\Phi_{c,i,t} = t2^c a_n + 2a_{n-1} - 3c a_n \geq (2^c - 3c)a_n \geq 0.$$

Thus we may assume $i \leq 2c$.

First let $t \geq 1$, so $n \leq i-1$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} D_1 + L_{c,i,t} &= a_{i-1}a_n - a_i a_{n-1} + 2b_{i-1}a_{n-1} - b_{i-2}a_n - b_i a_{n-2} \\ &= (h_{i-1}a_n - h_i a_{n-1}) + (b_{i-1}a_{n-1} - b_i a_{n-2}). \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 6 and log-concavity of (a_j) ,

$$\frac{h_i}{h_{i-1}} \leq \frac{a_{i-1}}{a_{i-2}} \leq \frac{a_n}{a_{n-1}},$$

with the case $n = 0$ interpreted directly; hence $h_{i-1}a_n - h_i a_{n-1} \geq 0$. Lemma 7, together with the monotonicity of the ratios a_j/a_{j-1} , gives $b_{i-1}a_{n-1} - b_i a_{n-2} \geq 0$. Finally $D_0, D_1 \geq 0$ by log-concavity of (a_j) and $n \leq i-1$. Hence (21) follows.

Now let $t = 0$, so $n = i$. If $i = 0$, then (21) is trivial. If $1 \leq i \leq 2c-1$, then two applications of Lemma 6 give

$$\frac{h_{i+1}}{h_{i-1}} \leq \frac{a_i}{a_{i-2}},$$

again with missing negative-index terms interpreted as zero. Hence

$$\Phi_{c,i,0} = a_i h_{i-1} - a_{i-2} h_{i+1} + 2b_{i-1} a_{i-1} \geq 0.$$

For $i = 2c$, $h_{i+1} = -1$, so the same displayed expression is plainly nonnegative. Therefore each $E_{c,i,t} \geq 0$, and since $\binom{m}{t} \geq 0$ for integers $m \geq 0$, (19) follows. \square

Theorem 3. *For all $a, c \geq 0$, the polynomial $P_{a,c}(x)$ is log-concave.*

Proof. The case $a = 0$ is Theorem 2. Suppose $P_{a,c}$ is log-concave. Since $xU_{a,c}(x)$ is a shift of the real-rooted polynomial $(1+x)^a A(x)^c$, it is log-concave. Also

$$P_{a+1,c} = P_{a,c} + xU_{a,c}.$$

The log-concavity gap of this sum is the sum of the two individual gaps and the mixed gap in Lemma 8. Hence $P_{a+1,c}$ is log-concave. Induction on a proves the result. \square

7 The subtraction family

Recall

$$R_{b,c}(x) = (x+2)^b \{B(x)^c + xC(x)^c\} - (1+x)^c.$$

Put

$$U_{b,c}(x) = (x+2)^b \{B(x)^c + xC(x)^c\} = \sum_i u_i x^i, \quad d_i = \binom{c}{i}.$$

For $0 \leq i \leq c$, set $e_i = d_i/u_i$, and set $e_i = 0$ for $i > c$. Then the coefficient of $R_{b,c}$ is $u_i(1 - e_i)$.

Lemma 9. *For all $b, c \geq 0$, $U_{b,c}(x)$ has a log-concave coefficient sequence.*

Proof. The polynomial $B(x)^c + xC(x)^c$ is the reversal of $A(x)^c + xB(x)^c$. Therefore it is log-concave by Theorem 2. Multiplication by $(x+2)^b$ preserves log-concavity by Lemma 1. \square

Lemma 10 (ratio convexity). *For all $b, c \geq 0$,*

$$e_0 \geq e_1 \geq \cdots \geq e_c \geq e_{c+1} = 0$$

and

$$e_{i-1} - 2e_i + e_{i+1} \geq 0 \quad (1 \leq i \leq c).$$

Proof. The assertion is immediate for $c = 0$, so assume $c \geq 1$. Let

$$R_i = \frac{u_i}{u_{i-1}}, \quad \rho_i = \frac{d_i}{d_{i-1}} = \frac{c-i+1}{i} \quad (1 \leq i \leq c),$$

and put $\rho_{c+1} = 0$. By Lemma 9, $R_{i+1} \leq R_i$.

Write

$$U_{b,c} = T_{b,c} + S_{b,c}, \quad T_{b,c} = (x+2)^b B(x)^c, \quad S_{b,c} = x(1+x)^c (x+2)^{b+c}.$$

For $1 \leq i \leq c$, write $B(x) = (1+\alpha x)(1+\beta x)$ with $\alpha = (3+\sqrt{5})/2 < 3$ and $\beta = (3-\sqrt{5})/2$. After ignoring the constant factor in $(x+2)^b$, the polynomial $T_{b,c}$ is an elementary-symmetric generating polynomial with c variables equal to α , c variables equal to β , and b variables equal to $1/2$. Thus (2) gives

$$\frac{T_i}{T_{i-1}} \geq \frac{3c + b/2 - (i-1)\alpha}{i} \geq \frac{3(c-i+1)}{i} = 3\rho_i.$$

For $2 \leq i \leq c$, applying (2) to $S_{b,c} = xW_{b,c}$, where $W_{b,c} = (1+x)^c(x+2)^{b+c}$, gives

$$\frac{S_i}{S_{i-1}} \geq L_i := \frac{3c+b-2i+4}{2(i-1)}.$$

Consequently, for $2 \leq i \leq c$,

$$R_i \geq \min\{3\rho_i, L_i\}, \quad L_i - \rho_i = \frac{bi+ci+2c+2}{2i(i-1)} > 0. \quad (22)$$

Also

$$R_1 = \frac{u_1}{u_0} = 3c + \frac{b}{2} + 2^c \geq 2c = 2\rho_1.$$

These lower bounds imply $R_i \geq \rho_i$, hence $e_i/e_{i-1} = \rho_i/R_i \leq 1$, so (e_i) is decreasing.

For convexity, for $1 \leq i < c$ we have

$$\frac{e_{i-1} - 2e_i + e_{i+1}}{e_{i-1}} = 1 - 2\frac{\rho_i}{R_i} + \frac{\rho_i\rho_{i+1}}{R_iR_{i+1}}.$$

After multiplying by $R_iR_{i+1} > 0$, it is enough to prove

$$G_i := R_{i+1}(R_i - 2\rho_i) + \rho_i\rho_{i+1} \geq 0.$$

If $R_i \geq 2\rho_i$, this is immediate; in particular this handles $i = 1$. Assume $i \geq 2$ and $R_i < 2\rho_i$. Since $R_{i+1} \leq R_i$, we have

$$G_i \geq R_i(R_i - 2\rho_i) + \rho_i\rho_{i+1} =: F_i(R_i).$$

In this case (22) forces $R_i \geq L_i$, and $F_i(x)$ is increasing for $x \geq L_i$ because $L_i > \rho_i$. Thus $F_i(R_i) \geq F_i(L_i)$. A simplification gives

$$F_i(L_i) = \frac{P(b, c, i)}{4i(i-1)^2(i+1)},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} P(b, c, i) &= b^2i^2 + b^2i + 2bci^2 + 6bci + 4bc + 4bi + 4b \\ &\quad + c^2i^2 + c^2i + 16c^2 + 4ci^2 - 12ci + 32c + 4i^2 - 12i + 16. \end{aligned}$$

For $2 \leq i \leq c$, put $z = i - 2 \geq 0$ and $y = c - i \geq 0$. Then P becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & z^4 + 2z^3y + (2b+13)z^3 + z^2y^2 + (2b+18)z^2y + (b^2+18b+62)z^2 \\ & \quad + 5zy^2 + (14b+68)zy + (5b^2+56b+144)z + 22y^2 + (24b+112)y \\ & \quad + 6b^2 + 60b + 144, \end{aligned}$$

which has only positive coefficients. Hence $e_{i-1} - 2e_i + e_{i+1} \geq 0$ for $1 \leq i < c$.

It remains to consider the endpoint $i = c$. If $c = 1$, the inequality follows from $R_1 \geq 2\rho_1$. If $c \geq 2$, then

$$\frac{e_c}{e_{c-1}} = \frac{\rho_c}{R_c} \leq \frac{\rho_c}{L_c} = \frac{2(c-1)}{c(c+b+4)} \leq \frac{1}{2},$$

so $e_{c-1} - 2e_c + e_{c+1} = e_{c-1} - 2e_c \geq 0$. □

Theorem 4. For all $b, c \geq 0$, $R_{b,c}(x)$ has a log-concave nonzero coefficient sequence.

Proof. By Lemma 9, (u_i) is log-concave. By Lemma 10, (e_i) is decreasing and convex. Let $f_i = 1 - e_i$. With $\delta_i = e_{i-1} - e_i$, we have

$$f_i^2 - f_{i-1}f_{i+1} = (1 - e_i)(\delta_i - \delta_{i+1}) + \delta_i\delta_{i+1} \geq 0.$$

Thus (f_i) is log-concave after deleting possible leading zeros. The coefficients of $R_{b,c}$ are $u_i f_i$, a pointwise product of two log-concave sequences after deleting possible leading zeros. Lemma 1 proves the theorem. □

8 Proof of Theorem 1

For $a > 0$, formula (4) reduces to $x^{b+c+1}(x+2)^b$ times the reversal of $P_{a,c}$. Theorem 3 and Lemma 1 prove log-concavity. For $a = 0$, formula (5) reduces to $x^{b+c}R_{b,c}(x)$, and Theorem 4 applies. This completes the proof.

A Exact integer verification

The proof uses finite exact verification only for cleared integer inequalities:

- (i) Lemma 4 for $1 \leq c \leq 1470$;
- (ii) Lemma 5 for $1 \leq c \leq 1470$;
- (iii) the boundary cases $0 \leq c \leq 3$ in Lemma 8.

The accompanying C++ file `verify_spider_structures.cpp` uses `boost::multiprecision::cpp_int` and no floating-point arithmetic. A run with parameters `1470 12` verifies these finite inequalities, performs an additional sanity check of the binomial-basis coefficients in Lemma 8 for $c \leq 8$, and directly checks the domination-polynomial log-concavity for $0 \leq a, b, c \leq 12$.

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